

ADVAGEN

DELIVERABLE REPORT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101069743 (ADVAGEN). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Development of ADVanced next GENERation Solid-State batteries for Electromobility Applications
GA n° 101069743

Start date of project: 01/08/2022
Duration of project: 48 months
Deliverable n° & name: D8.2. Website
Version 4
Work Package n° 8
Due date of D: M6, 31/01/2023
Actual date of D: 31/01/2023
Participant responsible: ABEE
Main authors: Takwa Benissa

Nature of the Deliverable			
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)		
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs		
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.		X

Dissemination Level			
PU	Public, fully open		X
SEN	Sensitive		

Quality procedure			
Date	Version	Reviewers	Comments
31 /01/2023	2	Rahul Gopalakrishnan	Overall revision
16/06/2023	3	Takwa Benissa	Corrections as per Martha GIALAMPOUKI's request
19/06/2023	4	Cécile Fligny	Corrections as per Martha GIALAMPOUKI's request

Project summary

This report is one of the deliverables from the "ADVAGEN" (Development of ADVAnced next GENeration Solid-State batteries for Electromobility Applications) project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101069743.

To date, the battery market is dominated by lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries, as the energy density has more than doubled, and their costs have dropped by a factor of at least 10. However, conventional Li-ion batteries (LIB) are reaching their performance limits regarding energy density and facing safety issues. As such, this requires developing and producing new battery generations, such as Solid-State Batteries (SSBs), so a new industry value chain in Europe towards their commercialization is created. Consequently, high-energy-density EU-made SSBs will ensure the supply of, among others, the automotive sector. To do so, developing and deploying new manufacturing technologies, enabling large-scale production of SSBs, is crucial. Indeed, among the overarching themes to develop and produce sustainable batteries in the future, the BATTERY 2030+ roadmap considers manufacturability as a cross-cutting key area. Innovative and scalable manufacturing techniques to produce SSBs will accelerate cost reduction, energy savings, and enhanced safety. ADVAGEN will develop a new lithium metal (LiM) battery cell technology based on a safe, reliable, and high-performing hybrid solid-state electrolyte (LLZO-Sulfide based), gaining a competitive advantage over the worldwide (mainly Asian) competition. This will sustainably strengthen the EU as a technological and manufacturing leader in batteries, as specified in the ERTRAC electrification roadmap and SET-Plan Action Point-7. ADVAGEN consortium contains key EU actors in the battery sector, from industrial materials producers (such as CPT), and battery manufacturers (such as ABEE) to R&D centers (IKE, CEA, IREC, TUB, CICE, POLITO, INEGI, UL, FEV) and the automotive industry (TME), covering the complete knowledge and value chain. ADVAGEN aims to re-establish European competitiveness in battery cell production by developing high-performance, affordable, and safe batteries.

Objective and Executive Summary

The present document delivers a general overview of the structure and contents of the ADVAGEN project website. It reflects, at this stage of the project, the current status and the planned content and features evolution that will be settled along with the project's progress. Possible future modifications and improvements might be identified to address any needs not identified at the time of writing this report. The website provides the main point of initial contact and information to the audience and other researchers. Based on what is requested in WP8 (communication and dissemination), the website has been designed to be professional, dynamic and market-facing. It will be regularly maintained during the lifetime of the project. It is intended to publish general content on the project and the updates and news of the project's advancement for a collaborative work environment and to facilitate the interaction with the consortium.

List of partners

N°	Name	Short name	Country
1	AVESTA BATTERY & ENERGY ENGINEERING	ABEE	BE
2	INEGI - INSTITUTO DE CIENCIA E INOVACAO EM ENGENHARIA MECANICA E ENGENHARIA INDUSTRIAL	INEGI	PT
3	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	IT
4	FEV EUROPE GMBH	FEV	DE
5	COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVE	CEA	FR
6	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG	TUBS	DE
7	CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA DE ENERGIAS ALTERNATIVAS FUNDACION, CIC ENERGIGUNE FUNDAZIOA	CICE	ES
8	FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	IREC-CERCA	ES
9	TOYOTA MOTOR EUROPE NV	TME	BE
10	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJAN	UL	SI
11	EUROQUALITY SARL	EQY	FR
12	TECHCONCEPTS BV	TC	NL
13	CERAMIC POWDER TECHNOLOGY AS	CERPOTECH	NO
14	IKERLAN S. COOP	IKERLAN	ES

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Introduction

The ADVAGEN website was designed to disseminate the work to the general audience and experts in the battery field. It will provide detailed and updated information about the ADVAGEN project objectives and activities. It will be constantly updated with material such as upcoming meetings, participation in events, dissemination actions, conferences, publications, whitepapers, newsletters, news, photos, etc. ADVAGEN website was structured to be a crucial tool for communications between project partners, stakeholders, and the wider public to share project outcomes (including access to deliverables and publications in accordance with the IPR protection), news, events, and an intranet under development (a private collaborative space). This intranet will be accessible by all partners and used for both communication purposes and document sharing.

The project partner in charge (ABEE) has designed the layout based on the graphic chart and will maintain the website content during the project's lifetime and at least 6 years after the end of the project. The purchase of a 6-years hosting plan will ensure the platform's sustainability after the project's end. A domain name was booked as follows:

www.advagen.eu/

With simple access to the Internet, the general public will be able to visualize and explore the website. Finally, statistics will be analysed to allow partners to locate the visitors' centers of interest and adjust the website content, which will be updated and produced mainly as part of WP8 – Task 8.2 Organisation of communication activities. The aim is to measure the digital impact of the project, collecting information like the number of users per month, users per country, the average duration of visits, and the number of visits to the news section.

Furthermore, Euroquality partner is responsible for creating the project’s graphic identity as the basis for all communication tools and social media channels associated with the website. ADVAGEN is present on social media and, at the time of writing this report, has Twitter and LinkedIn accounts. Their links are accessible on the ADVAGEN webpage.

The project website

At its early stage, only the generic pages describing the project’s objective, used technology, vision, solution, and consortium overview are populated. Later on, additional publications and sensitive deliverables will be added. As a part of the activities of WP8, the ADVAGEN website will be updated regularly by the project management team during its lifetime. The overall available content has been collected from all the ADVAGEN partners and used as the base for the first iteration of the WEB portal.

It is currently organized in various mock-ups and presented based on a typical structure derived from other EU projects.

Home page Tab

The portal's home page delivers the front-end message of the ADVAGEN project to communicate its objectives, the technology used for this project, the proposed solution, and its latest news and presentation to the consortium members.

The home page is organised according to the following design model:

Top of the page (Figure 1)

- Visual identity of ADVAGEN
- Menu items: Homepage, Consortium, News, Contact Us

The central part of the page

- Project background, ADVAGEN positioning overview,
- “Discover” button: Aim of the project, a description of the solution used, the impact of the project, its objectives, as well as a mapping of ADVAGEN partners (Figure 2)
- Latest news: visual and animated banner with the project updates (Figure 3)
- Horizon Europe message disclaimer (Figure 4)
- Social Media icon buttons: Twitter, LinkedIn (Figure 5)

Figures 1 to 5 below represent the home page in terms of header and main menu, footer, menu details, home page main content disclaimer, and social media.

Figure 1. Header and Menu

What we aim to do.

To date, the battery market is dominated by lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries, as the energy density has more than doubled and their costs have dropped by a factor of at least 10. However, conventional Li-ion batteries are reaching their performance limits in terms of energy density and additional features are needed to ensure safe batteries.

Development and production of new battery generations.

New battery generations is required, such as **Solid-State Batteries (SSBs)** as well as the creation of a new industry value chain in Europe towards their commercialization. To do so, **the development and deployment of new manufacturing technologies**, enabling the large-scale production of SSBs, is crucial.

Therefore, it is key to develop next solid-state battery generations with **innovative and scalable manufacturing techniques to accelerate cost reduction, energy savings, and enhanced safety** and enable its implementation in commercial applications

Figure 2. The “Homepage” tab and its subentries

Figure 3. Latest news section

Figure 4. Horizon Europe message disclaimer

Figure 5. Contact and social media section

Consortium Tab

The ADVAGEN consortium consists of a transdisciplinary consortium of 14 partners from 9 countries with ample experience in battery technology and product development.

This section groups all partners contributing to this project, their descriptions, roles within the project, photos of their facilities/ key persons involved, and a direct link to their websites (Figures 6, 7).

Figure 6. List of partners

Figure 7. Partner description example

News Tab

The “News” page is intended to disseminate the latest updates on the project’s activity. The news section is divided into two sections:

- “ALL” subtab: all kinds of activities and news will be posted there, for instance, articles, posts etc.. This page will be constantly updated with the latest material, such as dissemination actions, conferences, publications, whitepapers, newsletters, news, photos, etc.
- “Events” Subtab: Illustrates the dissemination activities related to events, the agenda of the project meetings (the Kick-off meeting, general assembly, etc.), upcoming meetings, participation in events

Figure 8 gives a representation of the “News” page with a photo of the kick-off meeting and a brochure of advertisement of the signature of a memorandum of understanding between ADVAGEN and SPINMATE partners for knowledge sharing as a part of a clustering activity.

Latest News

Discover here our latest news about the ADVAGEN project.

ALL

EVENTS

Events on 8 December 2022

Launch of the
ADVAGEN Project

READ MORE

Events on 21 January 2023

New partnership with
the SPINMATE project.

READ MORE

Figure 8. News page

Contact us Tab

A contact form is offered on the “Contact Us” page to the user connected to the project website. It requires entering personal data to submit a message to the ADVAGEN project.

Personal data are:

- Name
- E-mail address
- Subject
- Message: a body in free text
- Subscription to the project newsletter check box.

Figure 9 illustrates a representation of the contact form.

Contact us

Advagen fits your needs ? Contact us here

Your name

Your email

Subject

Your message (optional)

By submitting this e-mail, you allow us to use your e-mail in order to keep you informed about this project.

Figure 9. Contact form

Conclusion

Deliverable D8.2 has outlined the planned approaches and some early-stage activities that have been taken to the main component of the dissemination and communication actions for the ADVAGEN project.

The project website also provides information regarding the project outcomes, its socio-economic and environmental impact, and some statistical reports on website traffic (extracted from Google Analytics).

This deliverable is part of Task 8.2: Organisation of communication activities performed under WP7: Communication, dissemination, exploitation, and networking activities. For that reason, the content of the website will be continuously updated with dissemination material until the completion of the project. Updated website information (i.e., updated screenshots showing events, news, “traffic” and more detailed analytics) can be presented in future deliverables related to this Task, more specifically in D8.3, which will be submitted on M48.